

INCENTIVE WP1 T1.1
Interviews notes

Interviewee 1:

- Representation and Position:

Organization: Public university

Position: Assistant Professor

- Organization's Involvement in Citizen Science (CS) Projects:

Years Associated: Since 2020

Role in CS Projects: Initiator, collaborator, and contributor

- Identification of Project Partners:

Finding Partners: Through past collaborations

- Administrative Structures for CS Projects:

Existence: Not aware of any

Assessment: Unsure of the potential benefit

- Ease of Participation in CS Projects:

Finds it relatively easy, citing previous experiences

- Role of Administrative Structures in CS Projects:

Facilitate long-term storage, functionality, and continuity of tools and datasets

- Critical Factors for Successful Administrative Structure:

Long-term continuity and archiving of tools and datasets

- Collaboration with Schools/Universities:

Collaboration: Yes

Added Value: Wider network, greater diversity of expertise

- Challenges in CS Projects (from personal experience):

Challenges: Difficulty in addressing real-time needs of citizen scientists, especially in fixing errors without taking the entire challenge offline

- Skills Required for CS Projects:

Beyond Scientific Training: Understanding of specific communities, diversity within them, and awareness of biases, beliefs, and incentives

- Future Vision for CS:

Hopeful Trend: Continuation and growth with increased community involvement in question-asking and answering, not just data collection or annotation

- Impact of Coronavirus on CS Work:

Easier online participant recruitment

- Success Factors of a Specific CS Project:

Excellent technical support, engaged community, tapping into the expertise of a longstanding community, effective beta testing, advertising, and promotion

- Consideration of CS Project Results in Local/Regional Decisions:

Expresses hope that the results are considered

Interviewee 2:

- Representation and Position:

Organization: undefined

Role: retired (former ordinary professor)

- Organization's Involvement in Citizen Science (CS) Projects:

Years Associated: >4 years

Role in CS Projects: Initiator and collaborator

- Identification of Project Partners:

Contacting Partners: Through word of mouth, past collaborations, and mass media

- Ease of Participation in CS Projects:

Difficulty: Moderately easy

- Role of Administrative Structures in CS Projects:

Accomplishment: Informing about project possibilities, organizing events for idea exchange

Importance for Success: Communication of services, need for infrastructure support for scientists

- Vision for a CS Hub:

Components: Staff support for project setup and technical implementation

Channels: Hub channels to recruit staff from the community

- Impact of Establishing a CS Hub in RPFO:

Extra funding, extra personnel, legal, or other administrative modifications

- Collaboration with Schools/Universities:

Current Status: No collaboration at the moment

Potential Added Value: Enabling involvement of a large community

- Challenges in CS Projects (from personal experience):

Challenges: Technical implementation for citizen participation, supervision of participating citizens

- Skills Required for Running CS Projects:

Key Skills: Time investment in citizen care, effective communication, collaborators for regular citizen communication

- Future Vision for CS:

Expectation: Evolution of best practices over time, significant role in future research in suitable areas

- Impact of Coronavirus on CS Work:

Continuation of work online, scheduling Zoom appointments for discussions with citizens

- Consideration of CS Project Results in Local/Regional Decisions:

Influence: Indirect influence rather than immediate societal interest

- Final Thoughts on CS-Projects:

Emphasizes the importance of local knowledge, language, and local character for CS projects to reach society and make scientific work known to the broader public.

Interviewee 3:

- Representation and Position:

Organization: Higher Education Institute

Role: Professor

- Organization's Involvement in Citizen Science (CS) Projects:

Emerged around 2002-2003, primarily related to environmental projects

Role in CS Projects: Initiator and collaborator, Typically initiates Citizen Science projects; sometimes invited by other partners/collaborators

- Role of Administrative Structures in CS Projects:

Potential Benefits: Anticipates a Citizen Science hub enhancing the university's profile

Bureaucratic Concerns: Acknowledges the need to address bureaucracy-related issues

Preferred Participants: Suggests involvement of students, academic staff, policymakers, and social stakeholders

Community Engagement: Emphasizes starting with small local communities as advertisers/ambassadors before engaging larger communities

- Vision for a CS Hub:

Support Focus: Aims to support researchers and students interested in integrating citizen science into their research

Functions: Should provide necessary information, material, tools, and guidelines while eliminating bureaucratic procedures

Hub Involvement: Suggests involvement of researchers, students, and academic staff in running and managing the hub

Incentives and Framework: Stresses the need for well-defined incentives to involve and motivate participants and a long-term financial framework

Record of Best Practices: Proposes recording best practices from all scientific sectors

- Challenges in CS Projects (from personal experience):

Engage policymakers and convince citizens to participate

- Final Thoughts on CS-Projects:

Suggests exploring fields such as philosophy or humanities for potential citizen science practices

Interviewee 4:

- Representation and Position:

Organization: Higher Education Institute

Role: Researcher

- Organization's Involvement in Citizen Science (CS) Projects:

Emerged around 2002-2003

Role in CS Projects: Initiator and collaborator

- Perception and Involvement in Citizen Science Initiatives:

Initial Perception: Initially viewed as involving citizens for data collection and processing, not necessarily as part of the "citizen science" field

Unconscious Participation: Suggests that citizen science activities may have occurred, consciously or unconsciously, during the development of various theses

- Role of Administrative Structures in CS Projects:

Support Focus: Aims to support researchers and students interested in integrating citizen science into their research

Functions: Should provide necessary information, material, tools, and guidelines while eliminating bureaucratic procedures

Hub Involvement: Suggests involvement of researchers, students, and academic staff in running and managing the hub

- Vision for a CS Hub:

Perceived Usefulness: Believes it would be beneficial for research topics requiring citizen participation and establishing a channel with society

- Challenges in CS Projects (from personal experience):

Difficulty in attracting and maintaining citizen interest in research projects

- Consideration of CS Project Results in Local/Regional Decisions:

Unsure if the results of CS initiatives are considered for policymaking

Believes utilization of results would be ideal for the future of the country in various sectors

- Final Thoughts on CS-Projects:

Communication: Stresses the importance of speaking the same language as citizens, making them feel part of the process and co-shapers of research

Target Audience: Challenges in attracting those who usually abstain from civic participation